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ABSTRACT

Historically, animal characters and animal-child encounters in children’s narratives have served largely metaphorical functions. More recently, scholars have become interested in exploring literary human-animal relations as interesting in and of themselves and not purely as background for promoting values and attitudes considered desirable for adolescent readers. The article proposes a reading of Mary O’Hara’s novel *My Friend Flicka* (O’Hara 1941) which embeds the relationship between the human protagonist and the horse in the wider stories of equine domestication and the settling of the Western frontier. In effect, while the story of Ken and Flicka is read as a metaphor – a synecdoche even – it is not a metaphor of human-human encounters but of the contradictions and ethical dilemmas inherent to the process of human-directed animal domestication in a capitalist settler colonial society. Ken’s coming of age through the story of love and loss is representative of dilemmas that humans engaged in processes of domestication have had to grapple with: Ken must come to terms with the violence of domestication. Concurrently, Flicka’s story of pain, fear, and love is read not just as the unique story of an individual horse but of the generations of equines that have been forced to adapt to an environment shaped by human dominance.

Domestication Western-Style: Fantasies of Harmony and the Violence of Plasticity in Mary O'Hara's *My Friend Flicka*

[T]he more one really knows domestic animals, the less domestic they seem.

Barney Nelson, *The Wild and the Domestic*, 24

1. Introduction

Mary O'Hara's Wyoming Trilogy (*My Friend Flicka*, 1941; *Thunderhead*, 1943; *Green Grass of Wyoming*, 1946) is populated by liminal horses, which fluidly traverse the wild/domesticated boundary, revealing it as constructed and impermanent in ways that underscore the laborious deconstruction of this binary in recent decades by critics from the environmental humanities. Most of the horses in O'Hara's novels are born on the open range without human presence and are then brought down onto the ranch, where they are tamed and trained. Some return to the wild; a mustang known as the Albino lures mares away from the ranch, but his progeny rejoin the ranch herd, though their sire is never captured by humans. Freedom is less the result of interrupting the extended process of domestication and more of an opportunity: an open gate, a damaged fence. It is also a currency: Flicka's son Thunderhead is rewarded with freedom for killing the Albino, revealing a framework in which equine freedom is a value but also one in which active steps need to be constantly undertaken in order to safeguard the fragile effects of domestication. This wild/domestic dialectic, the plasticity of equine figures, is steeped in symbolic associations. The horses' desire for freedom accentuates the wild mustang's status as a symbol of unbreakable will, defiance, and independence. Still, close and affectionate bonds do form between humans and horses as a result of domestication—after all, this is the story of love between Ken and Flicka. The ebb and flow of animals into and out of the domestic fold creates a surface image of human-animal harmony, a Western utopia offering—literally to the equine characters but figuratively also to the readers—the best of both worlds: the wild and the domesticated.

However, this surface image of harmony breaks down upon careful inspection. Unlike most children's literature of the period, O'Hara's books do not portray the companion animals' love of their humans as boundless and unconditional. On the contrary, they carefully reveal the conditions of domestication as not only impermanent but also implicated in a certain primal violence: the capture, containment, gelding, branding, and breaking of horses.

Domestication here is plastic: the shaping of the equine body into the domesticated form is like the stretching of a rubber band. If stretched too far, the band will snap; if pressure is released, the band will return to its original shape. The question of Flicka's plasticity constitutes the main dramatic tension in the book; for most of the novel, the reader wonders whether the filly will give in to Ken's domesticating pressure or die resisting it. While affective bonds are undoubtedly formed between humans and horses, the pleasure of interspecies encounters is not unconditional. Erica Fudge argues that another children's book from the same time period, Eric Knight's classic *Lassie-Come-Home*, projects the fantasy that animals love us and will go to great lengths to be with humans (Fudge 2008, 26–32). O'Hara's animals go to great lengths to leave us, and the stories reveal the measures that need to be taken in order to prevent their retreat.

Like much children's literature of the period, *My Friend Flicka* is a bildungsroman, but the maturation of the main character is rooted in a different paradigm than in other examples of the boy-and-animal genre. In most such stories—like Marjorie Kinnan Rawlings's *The Yearling* (1938) or Fred Gipson's *Old Yeller* (1956)—the loss of innocence is associated with the boys losing the beloved objects of their youthful desire, the accompanying disenchantment with figures of authority, or the shift in the child's identification with the world of nature to a painful but necessary identification with the world of adult humans. As Eric Tribunella argues in his insightful study of melancholia in children's literature, boys become men through the experience of loss, which is melancholically incorporated into their identity as men (Tribunella 2011, xiv–xvii). In *My Friend Flicka*, the horse survives, but this does not prevent the story from being a bildungsroman. Ken's maturation comes through the realization that his initial dream of interspecies love—based purely on mutual affection—is a fantasy. He does not lose the horse, but he loses the dream. In this respect, and despite the happy ending, *Flicka* is very much anti-Lassie.¹ It is significant that this early deconstruction of the Lassie myth takes place in a 'boy-and-horse' story, not a 'boy-and-dog' story. The specificity of the domestication story of the horse lends itself much better to deconstructing the fantasy of interspecies love, for it is clear that even though the domestication of all animals helped further human dominance, the story of the

¹ It should be noted that Eric Knight's *Lassie-Come-Home* was originally serialized in the *Saturday Evening Post* in 1938, shortly before O'Hara set out to write *My Friend Flicka*. However, Knight's *Lassie* was based in a plot pattern that was not original - a faithful dog's overcoming of obstacles to be reunited with the owner - but was already schematic by the 1930s. Stories about loving and loyal dogs had become very popular in the second half of the nineteenth century, both in the US and in the UK. In the 1940s, even the term 'a Lassie story' became a generic term for a story about canine love. For example, in 1947 Marjorie Kinnan Rawlings, the author of *The Yearling*, published a serialized novella titled *A Mountain Prelude* in the *Saturday Evening Post* and colloquially referred to it in her correspondence as 'my Lassie story.'

horse as a species is not only linked to the harnessing of the horse's body for human gains but also inseparable from acts of obvious and undeniable violence.

2. Lively Commodities and Encounter Value

One of the strategies O'Hara uses to deconstruct fantasies of pure interspecies love is to show how human-animal relations are embedded in the economic framework of capitalism. In *Animal Capital*, Nicole Shukin (2009) insightfully connects 'the semiotic currency of animal signs and the carnal traffic in animal substances' (7). The realization of this connection is also one of the marks of Ken's maturation. Like the main protagonist of *The Yearling*, who is forced to kill his beloved pet deer because the animal destroys the family's crops, Ken also grows to understand that human-animal relationships on the ranch are embedded in a broader economic framework. The horses are lively commodities and the family's survival is based on the humans' skill in increasing their market value. Ken's transformation is, in essence, a growing awareness of the realities of domestication: its embeddedness in both individual acts of violence and a broader economic (and anthropocentric) framework, which values animal utility.

O'Hara's trilogy, and especially the first book in the series, can be read as a synecdochal representation of a certain interpretation of the process of domestication. O'Hara is not preaching animal liberation, but she is providing aestheticized commentary on the practices and dilemmas of generations of humans involved in the raising, breeding, and training of companion animals, and she is most certainly interested in the ethics of domestication. The value of the Western setting lies in the unique possibilities it opens for condensing the story of domestication into a single generation: wild horses are tamed and then return to the wild. In this, O'Hara's fiction resembles Jack London's wolf-dog stories, *The Call of the Wild* (1903) and *White Fang* (1906). Both O'Hara and London also propose a vision of domestication that entails some form of original violence, which is a reading of domestication that is impossible to disentangle from the settler colonial framework which shapes the two authors' work.

Mary O'Hara's Wyoming Trilogy is set on the fictional Goose Bar Ranch, located between Laramie and Cheyenne, where Rob and Nell McLaughlin, transplants from the East, operate a cattle and horse ranch. The horses are raised on the open range, where they lead a semi-wild life and are brought in for breaking and training. While out on the range, the mares live in herds, or harems, protected by the stallion, whose role is that of the ranch patriarch and a stand-in for the authority of the ranch owner. Rob McLaughlin and the Goose Bar Ranch stallion Banner share a powerful affective relationship, which Rob sees as rooted in mutual

respect and a sense of shared responsibility: ‘Banner and his father together ran the ranch’ (O’Hara 1941, 30). Rob’s firm but empathic authority as the boss of the ranch is mirrored in Banner’s kind but firm handling of the mares; for example, the stallion manages to herd a spooked mare back to the other horses as she is heading towards a cliff. It is not coincidental that Banner is not saddlebroken and is the only ungelded male horse on the ranch. Other horses, after being broken in for the saddle, are usually sold: a process that forms the essence of the economic viability of the ranch. They can be thought of as lively capital (Haraway 2008, 45–47) or lively commodities, a term coined by Rosemary-Claire Collard and Jessica Dempsey to refer to ‘commodities whose capitalist value is derived from their status as living beings’ (2013, 2684). The observations Donna Haraway makes when coining this term to conceptualize value-added dogs apply here as well: encounter value, understood as the relationship formed in the process of interacting with the horses, not only significantly affects the humans’ perception of the individual horses but is also reflected in the prices the horses fetch on the market. A recent anthropological analysis of the mustang market reveals that ‘companionability is a prerequisite for mustangs’ marketability and a central aspect for the emergence of encounter value’ (Putz 2021, 585). A ‘biddable’ horse, well-trained and generally socialized with humans, is worth more than one which is skittish and flighty. At the same time, encounter value is what safeguards the horses from becoming purely a form of exploitable biocapital.

Encounter value, market value, and domestication, or the level of a horse’s tameness and tractability, are all intimately connected and are modulated through a number of biopolitical technologies that operate both via physical alterations of the horses’ appearance (breeding selection and control of horses’ reproduction) and behavior (training). Even though training is sometimes thought of as the ‘culture’ to the ‘nature’ of breeding, these two modalities, operating on the potential animal via breeding selection and on the existing animal via physical alteration and training, are actually inseparable (Włodarczyk 2018, 7). They can be viewed as technologies of domestication enabled by the plasticity of the species *equus caballus*, but always undergirded by some level of physical violence: a fact which the series, especially the first book, reflects on quite openly. This link between (plastic) adaptation and (inevitable) coercion brings to mind the understanding of plasticity proposed by Zakiyyah Jackson in *Becoming Human*. For Jackson, plasticity is always implicated in violence (2020, 3; 18-20): regardless of what technologies are applied, the shaping of the body is always to some extent coercive or is a response to initial trauma; it is a kind of compensation mechanism. While in Jackson’s thought plasticity shapes the overdetermined

Black(ened) body, her understanding of the concept can be applied to animal bodies as well, especially to the handling of animal bodies in the processes of taming and domestication.

The usefulness of Jackson's concept of plasticity lies in its capacity for exploding the fantasy of changing the animal other's behavior without any coercion, purely through love – the fantasy that is the starting point of Ken's attraction to Flicka. The boy wants Flicka to change and grow to love him, and he believes he can accomplish this without the use of force. Admittedly, for Jackson plasticity is mostly an explanatory literary trope: the curious potential of a fictional body to take on a very wide and often contradictory range of associations. However, it can also serve as a useful concept for bringing to the surface the violence of environmental pressure implied in the biological understandings of plasticity. Even in cases of phenotypic plasticity completely unrelated to domestication, the changes in the phenotype, or appearance, of the organism are an adaptation to altered environmental conditions: a drying up of a once-abundant food supply, the presence of a novel predator, climate change, the appearance of toxins in the environment (Pigliucci 2001, 1–28). In the case of domestic animals, the violence is often quite explicit: the organism needs to adapt to an environment in which humans are a central agent. While violence is not a category of biological analysis and not even a term in the vocabulary of an evolutionary biologist, it is a concept that connects the phenomena listed above in the perceptual framework of an environmental humanities scholar familiar with Foucault's ideas on power and violence. Generally, Foucault sees power as a relation that is productive, while violence is destructive (Foucault 2000, 341). Still, even for Foucault, violence can play a constitutive role in generating power relations: it can be a kind of original sin from which power relations emerge. And this seems to be the story we get in O'Hara's books, where original violence often initiates processes that can lead to the formation of strong affective bonds between humans and animals. Through descriptions of the technologies of domestication, O'Hara's books suggest that the plasticity of domestication is always enmeshed in a framework of at least coercion, and sometimes even overt violence.

3. The Violence of Domestication

While the distinction between coercion and violence can sometimes be difficult to pinpoint, O'Hara very explicitly provides the readers with scenes that are unambiguously violent; scenes that foreground extreme physical pain that can in no way be avoided through the animal's conduct. Some of the most overt forms of violence are related to the control of equine reproduction. Very unusually for a children's novel, *My Friend Flicka* includes a

gruesome scene of the gelding of two-year-old colts. The gelding is a solemn affair that seems to bring pleasure to no one: 'McLaughlin's face looked angry and strained' (O'Hara 1941, 74), and yet it is carried out as a necessary ritual, a rite of passage both for the horses and for the boys who are expected to watch: 'None of the men joshed or even spoke now while the vet worked, but the colt screamed and struggled terribly. Before the operation was over, he too was quiet, lying inert while the bright streams of his blood darkened on the sand. Doc's arms were red to the elbow. At last it was over' (75). Gender and species violence are brought together in this scene that elucidates the violence implicit in the euphemistic phrasing of the biological definition of domestication as 'control over sexual reproduction.' These forms of violence also emphasize the link between domesticity and domestication: it is not coincidental that de-sexing is one of the technologies of domestication, an association that has been explored in the context of companion animals by, among others, Clare Palmer and Karla Armbruster. These scholars echo each other in speaking of de-sexing as implicated in increasing 'placidity, docility, ... and a slackening in territoriality' (Palmer 2001, 357). Meanwhile, Susan McHugh, in a reading of a number of books that tackle animal sexuality, suggests that to fully understand cultural discourses of animal de-sexing, one needs to begin 'by situating them amid cultural problems that cutting reproductive organs out of bodies cannot solve' (Mc Hugh 2011, 117).

In the conversation that follows the gelding scene, Ken wants to know if the castration procedure alters the male horses. Rob answers:

Well, something's gone out of them, but it's something that's no use to men, except in a stud. . . Only the best blood should be passed on. And where you get wild horse colts growing up without gelding, there's indiscriminate breeding, and the stock runs down. That's why the mustangs have deteriorated on the plains in the West here. Only occasionally do you get really fine specimens, and then it's due to luck. (83)

Rob's answer reveals how embedded his position is in the then-dominant discourses on animal breeding (Kimmelman 1983; Derry 2015, 35–39), which have by now been disproved by contemporary population genetics. Mustangs, after all, are hardy animals adapted to their environment and do not breed 'indiscriminately.' However, Rob is refreshingly honest in his acknowledgement of humans' desire to control animal reproduction as an inevitable element of domestication. Rob acknowledges the changes in the desexed animals and conceptualizes them in terms of a lack but adds that this is not a lack that decreases the horse's utility, which is, after all, of key importance for the ranch as an economic enterprise. Rob's vision of

human-horse coexistence is based on the acknowledgment of the violence of domestication, which, however, does not preclude the development of meaningful relationships—of encounter value. Ken's initial reaction to witnessing the gelding is one of physical queasiness—'Sharp pains ran through him and sobs strangled him' (76)—largely because his desire for a colt is rooted in a fantasy of reciprocal interspecies love; a love that is pure and innocent, uncoerced but springing from the animal's desire to befriend a worthy human. Shortly after the gelding scene, Ken decides to opt for a filly instead of a male colt, a decision which can be read as his refusal to let go of the fantasy of domestication without violence.

The lead-in conflict in the first book of the trilogy, before the narrative begins to focus on the development of the relationship between young Ken McLaughlin and Flicka, concerns the boy's selection of the colt. Ken is seen by his father as an unreliable and disorganized boy, prone to daydreaming. His father's reluctant offering of a horse, at the urging of Ken's mother Nell, is supposed to elicit a transformation in the boy. The McLaughlins appear to be believers in the old adage—explicitly formulated in Locke's *Some Thoughts Concerning Education* (1693), popularized in the US through various educational publications throughout the nineteenth century but also practiced intuitively by generations of parents—that caring for an animal develops responsibility in children, especially in boys. It is telling that in explaining his decision Rob uses language that initiates Ken into a discourse in which hard work and rationality are linked with manhood: 'You're going to train the yearling. I'll give you a little help just with the first breaking, but you'll train her, and she'll train you. I want you to make a good pony out of her. I want her to make a man out of you' (O'Hara 84–85). Ken is promised a colt—'any colt up to a year old' (70)—but it is implied that the boy must choose wisely. By that, his father means that he should choose a horse that will be likely to make a trusty mount and a good partner for ranch work. After significant deliberation, Ken, however, goes against his father's wishes and chooses Flicka, a yearling filly his father considers completely unsuitable. Ken's attraction to Flicka is rooted in his admiration for 'her wild beauty and speed' (110); the first time Ken sees her, the filly is able to outrun other, adult horses. Conversely, Rob's dislike of Ken's decision is tied to his reading of Flicka as flighty and unstable, too wild: that which Ken finds attractive his father finds repulsive. Ken likes her independence; Rob warns him that a horse which is 'a lone wolf' (157), unsociable while in the company of other horses, may prove to be untrainable.

Rob's opinion is grounded in his understanding of heredity coupled with knowledge of his horses' lineage: Flicka is the offspring of Banner and Rocket, a mare whose sire is the wild Albino, a mustang who 'steals' Banner's mares. The entire group of the Albino's

descendants prove to be unbreakable and wild; the ranch hands use the term ‘loco’ to collectively describe the influence of the Albino’s ‘bad blood’ on this strain. The presence of the Albino stallion in the narrative is an overt incorporation of one of the famous myths of the West, the legend of the white stallion, or white steed, a wild mustang with an indomitable spirit that cannot be tamed (Atwood-Lawrence 1981; Phillips 2017, 178–86). Within Western lore, the white stallion is a figure of admiration and a phantasmatic icon of the American West (Atwood-Lawrence 1981, 86). In the vocabulary which I am using to frame my argument in this article, the white steed represents a lack of plasticity: he refuses all attempts at adapting to human presence. For Rob McLaughlin, the Albino is a threat not only because he lures mares away from the ranch, but also because his rigid wildness is passed onto his offspring. In fact, Flicka’s mother, Rocket, seemingly commits suicide while in transport to her new owner: the implication being that she chooses death over captivity. Angered by this experience, which also leaves him seriously injured — Rocket manages to bloody Rob’s face before fatally injuring herself—McLaughlin sells off all the remaining horses from the Albino’s line. All but one—Flicka, whom Ken has selected as his colt. While Rob’s understanding of the prepotency of ‘bad blood’ is more a reflection of the racist prescriptions on miscegenation popular at the time,² his desire to breed the horses that exhibit an inborn degree of tameness reflects a basic tenet of most theories of how animal domestication took place. Rob’s actions are a condensed representation of those of animal breeders over thousands of years.

4. Plasticity and Domestication

The current research on domestication suggests that historically—both in cases of supposed self-domestication and human-initiated domestication—individual animals with a greater inborn degree of tameness had an advantage over those which exhibited fear of or aggression towards humans. Dmitry Belyayev and Lyudmila Trut’s famous fox-taming experiment, carried out in the Soviet Union since the late 1950s, can be read as somewhat

² Rob claims that the Albino has prepotency (by which he understands that the stallion’s influence on the offspring is much greater than that of the mare) because of the high percentage of his ‘Arabian blood,’ which comes directly from ‘the Spanish horses’ from which mustangs originated. This is, of course, highly unlikely. Prepotent sires are those with a high coefficient of inbreeding (COI), and it is improbable that wild-bred populations would exhibit high COIs (Waring 2003). Eugenic discourses contained within them a paradox related to prepotency: it was a common belief at the time that especially smart or strong-willed individuals can have a greater effect on their progeny (Crew 1925), but it was also widely held that even a drop of ‘bad blood’ can spoil an entire breeding line. While this belief was common among animal breeders, it was also, of course, at the root of Jim Crow laws and was an element of eugenic discourses which were at the height of their popularity in the 1930s.

analogous to Rob MacLaughlin's project of taming wild horses, in that both the experiment and the fictional narrative by O'Hara deal—literally and metaphorically—with accelerating and maintaining domestication. In Belyayev's experiment, the foxes were selected for further breeding on the basis of one discrete criterion: tameness. One of the takeaways was that tameness in a wild species such as the fox could be significantly increased or decreased within a relatively short time span through human-directed selection. However, significant genetic variation for tameness within a species may constitute a prerequisite for commencing the process of domestication and may be a possible explanation for why some species have never been domesticated (Dugatkin and Trut 2017, 60). The variation for tameness within a species can also be thought of in terms of the behavioral plasticity of that species: the greater the plasticity of a given species, here understood as adaptability to a human-dominated environment, a kind of responsiveness to pressure, the more likely that species is to be domesticated. Plasticity is both a condition and a result of domestication: dogs exhibit greater behavioral plasticity than wolves, though some plasticity must have been present among wolves if they were capable of becoming domesticated. Returning to the McLaughlins' enterprise, Rob selects from among the horses that are already trainable those which can further contribute to his success as a rancher. Rob's preference for tractable animals makes perfect sense in light of the dominant views on the history of domestication, while also revealing the strong link between the degree of tameness and the animal's potential market value and, more broadly, the implication of domestication in a market economy: the horses are broken so that they can fetch a higher price, maintaining and investing in horses that cannot bring in profit counters the goals of the ranch as a business enterprise.

Another insight from Belyayev and Trut's fox experiment may also be brought up at this point: caretakers' propensity for developing affective bonds with the tamer and more sociable animals. After several generations of selection for tameness at the experimental fox farm, the fox pups were so endearingly cute and desirous of human contact that it was almost impossible for the caretakers to maintain the protocols of the experiment and not pick up the foxes and cuddle them (Dugatkin and Trut 2017, 105–8). On the other hand, no caretakers volunteered to work with the foxes in the aggressive control group (164–5). The observation from the fox experiment provides both an interesting comment on Haraway's notion of encounter value and another perspective for reading human-animal interactions at Goose Bar Ranch. It seems that for encounter value to be high, or for encounters among companion species to play out in beneficial ways, one needs to begin with subjects that are open to these encounters. Again, if Rob's actions are conceptualized in light of the logic of domestication,

his decision to sell the Albino's descendants by trailer-load and without profit is understandable: the horses seemed incapable of entering into encounters with humans.

Ken's initial dreams are clearly fueled by a fantasy, which obscures the realities of interspecies interaction. His attraction to the wild and the desire to tame the untamable can even be read as a metaphor for the mythology of the frontier. In the Western as a literary genre, the cowboy's ability to tame the wild 'white steed' is proof of the human character's exceptionalism: the horse will only submit to the wise and worthy human being (Atwood-Lawrence 1981, 83–7). In the narratives contributing to the formation of the mythology of the cowboy—the works of Zane Grey, Owen Wister, J. Frank Dobie, Will James—kindness to horses is an immediate identifying feature of a hero, while the mistreatment of horses is the mark of a villain. Still, scenes of breaking (or gentling, as the breaking of horses has also been called since the mid-nineteenth century) inevitably include the use of violence, dispensed with controlled precision and a steady temper, but unmistakable as violence. What shapes *My Friend Flicka* into more of a romance than a western is the focus on Ken's love for Flicka and, as Christine Doyle phrases it, a certain 'chaotic eroticism' (2008, 293). As an aside, this intense and almost erotic interspecies love is a frequent theme of a particular subgenre of children's fiction with which *My Friend Flicka* is associated: the boy and his animal story. Eric Tribunella suggests in *Melancholia and Maturation: The Use of Trauma in American Children's Literature* that the eroticism present in these juvenile books suggests a transitional phase. It must be a love lost if the boy is to progress to proper heterosexual relationships. The death of the animal—a theme one may initially find surprising for children's literature, but yet one so common that it basically defines the genre—is not only necessary in this progression but is additionally a practice of human losses to come (Tribunella 2011, xvii). Here, however, *My Friend Flicka* defies the template: the horse does not die. Still, even though the filly survives, the narrative remains a bildungsroman. It is a story of Ken's loss of innocence, though Flicka's death proves to be unnecessary for achieving this. Her domestication is sufficient for Ken's disillusionment and maturation.

As the novel opens, Ken is still full of juvenile and naive belief in the possibility of interspecies love without coercion. Because this is a coming-of-age story, he eventually grows to accept his father's wisdom, that is the knowledge that interspecies love without some initial violence is a fantasy, a storyline which can also be read—if we read the plot as a synecdochal representation of domestication—as Ken's acknowledgment of the violence inherent in the practices of domestication. The turning point is the capture of Flicka, a

particularly gruesome and bloody scene. Flicka, completely oblivious of Ken's love and unwilling to be captured, frantically avoids being roped, jumps out of a barn window once she is forced inside and ends up seriously injured after trying to clear a barbed-wire fence surrounding the pasture. Stunned, Ken looks on, completely unable to intervene and uncomprehending of why Flicka insists on running away despite his love for her: 'Then, seeing that there was no hope, she raced south towards the range where she had spent her life, gathered herself, and rose to the impossible leap. Each of the men watching had the impulse to cover his eyes, and Ken gave a howl of despair' (162). While a direct confrontation with a human does not take place, the primal scene of biopower here features a man-made object, designed for restricting the free movement of domestic animals—a fence. No whip, no bit, no violent struggle with the saddle was necessary for eliciting Flicka's submission. At this moment, Ken's illusion of the instant reciprocity of his love is shattered at the sight of Flicka's bloodied body: 'They stood in a circle watching while she kicked and fought and thrashed until the wire was tightly wound and tangled about her, piercing and tearing her flesh and hide. At last she was unconscious, streams of blood running on her golden coat, and pools of crimson widening on the grass beneath her' (162). It is hard for Ken to comprehend that just his presence near his beloved horse evokes fear, anguish, and physical pain in Flicka. Yet comprehend he does, and this process leads to a change in the boy; one which Nell, his mother, describes as Ken finally 'facing facts' (183).

At first though, conscious of the harm he has inflicted on his beloved horse, Ken begins to wish he could reverse time and release Flicka back into the wild. In many other wild animal stories for children, the implicit didactic message for the reader is that wild things belong in the wild: the captured animal is released; the emotional attachment is painfully severed; boundaries between the wild and the domestic are re-established. While this framework becomes a dominant one in the second half of the twentieth century, with Joy Adamson's *Born Free* (1960) signaling a paradigm change that turns into a staple plot device by the time *Free Willy* becomes a box office success in 1993, it is not unusual in earlier texts, also in wild horse stories. For example, Marguerite O'Henry's *Misty of Chincoteague* (1947), a popular American book relatively contemporary to O'Hara's *My Friend Flicka*, features a pair of siblings who manage to capture a wild horse, Phantom, only to eventually release her back to her wild herd once they recognize that, even though she grows fond of them, she does not belong with them. Dawn Heinecken reads O'Henry's novel as a lesson in recognizing and respecting animal agency (Heinecken 2017, 27–8). Yet, this is not the lesson of O'Hara's Flicka. The dream of releasing the mare back into the wild is presented as a juvenile fantasy

of going back in time that Ken needs to overcome. He needs to learn that violence cannot be undone, but that it can lead to something formative. This is the lesson of domestication.

5. Make Her Love You: Shaping Non-Human Desire

Such recognition of the productive potential of destruction is the gist of philosopher Catherine Malabou's understanding of plasticity, though her thinking is influenced more by neurobiology and the reaction of the brain to trauma, not by evolutionary biology and the reaction of species to environmental change. Influenced by Foucault's understanding of power as a productive force, Malabou writes: 'Yet destruction too is formative . . . The fact that all creation can only occur at the price of a destructive counterpart is a fundamental law of life. It does not contradict life; it makes life possible' (Malabou 2012, 4). The effects of Flicka's violent resistance to capture are the beginning of her new life: Flicka does not die but is seriously injured in a way that makes it impossible for her to further protest Ken's constant presence. He can attend to the filly and nurse her precisely because she is incapacitated. It is only out of the violent end of Flicka's previous existence and the bruises to her body inflicted by the barbed wire that the peaceful multispecies encounters Ken longs for can develop. Ken had not recognized Flicka's agency, the possibility of Flicka having her own dreams and desires, and Flicka's behavior upon capture makes him realize his mistake. While recognition of animal agency is necessary for meaningful interspecies relationships to develop, recognition of agency does not necessarily entail full respect for the animal's agency—once agency is recognized, it can be shaped, molded, and structured. This observation has been historically employed by animal trainers who skillfully manipulate an animal's desires in the process of training (Włodarczyk 2018). This is also the lesson Ken learns from his father.

With Flicka teetering on the brink of life, injured and in pain, Rob conveys to Ken the possibility of structuring Flicka's experience of confinement in a way that will make her desire Ken's presence:

'There's one thing that will help you, Ken.'

'What?'

'Her sickness and misery. When you take away everything, freedom, friends, home, habits, happiness, from a living creature, almost life itself, it will turn, in sheer need and desperation, to the one thing that is left. And that's you.'

'Me.' Ken had never felt so important.

'Yes. You are her whole world. Make her like it.' (187)

What Rob proposes is a subtle technique of biopower, more subtle than brute physical submission enacted in the classic western rendition of horse-breaking, one which is based on a modulation of the horse's desire through the association of human presence with access to desirable resources. It is a technique that requires much more time and effort than the classic rationality of discipline, and one which results in a stronger affective relationship between horse and trainer. As a result of the incident, Ken grows to understand that the possibility of the human-horse relationship is unavoidably rooted in an imbalance of power between the two subjects and in the human's control of the horse. This recognition in no way diminishes his love for Flicka, but it does shape his perception of the relationship differently: it is, on the one hand, imbued with Ken's guilt, but also with a growing sense of responsibility. This is a love that is no longer purely in the realm of fantasy: it makes him aware of the productive potential of power, but it also makes him abandon his naive dream of human-equine harmony.

After reading the scene of Flicka's capture and of Ken's soliloquy after the event—Flicka, you're the one I want . . . I won't leave you again . . . never, Flicka. I don't want those other horses. *They're nothing, just simply nothing at all.* And you're my responsibility. That's what Dad said. I pulled you in from the range where you were wild and could take care of yourself, and I've made you so you can't' (179–80)—it is hard to not draw parallels between domestication and domesticity, between the taming of wild horses and heterosexual romance. It has already been mentioned that it is not coincidental that so many American horse stories from the first half of the twentieth century, unlike British horse stories, feature male protagonists (Doyle 2008). Also unlike their British counterparts, these Western stories focus on the taming of wild mustangs against the backdrop of a settler-colonial culture in the process of Westward expansion. Ken's recognition of the realities of domestication is thus coupled with a growing recognition of his place in the world as a man.

In the end, Ken does succeed in making Flicka love him, which paves the way for showcasing the wide range of biopolitical technologies applied in the breaking of horses. Training can also be conceptualized as another technology for increasing the plasticity of equine bodies, one which works in addition to and in tandem with breeding selection: the behavior of the horses changes as a result of the techniques applied by the humans, though one of the concerns of the book is that such shaping is impossible with some horses—the Albino's get is tainted with 'bad blood.' Because the ranch is a business enterprise, it needs to operate with a focus on profit, so horse-breaking needs to be an efficient business, which

maximizes the ratio of gain/effort. At the same time, however, the horses are lively commodities and encounter value becomes an additional variable, one which is largely absent from interactions with non-lively commodities: emotional attachments are formed between trainers and horses, and empathy develops. This is why Rob uses as little force as possible in his methods of horse-breaking: on the one hand, training horses is his livelihood, on the other, he clearly understands that the process is not a pleasant one for the subjects of training and tries to minimize the discomfort out of empathic concern for the horses' well-being. Such empathy in practices of animal husbandry is insightfully explored in the work of Jocelyne Porcher, who speaks of the collaborative nature of the labor of farm animals and their caretakers (2017). Such empathy is also one reason why McLaughlin is reluctant to employ so-called bronco busters, farmhands who travel from ranch to ranch breaking the owners' horses. For Rob, the methods of the bronco busters are too confrontational.

However, the training of Flicka can be carried out completely differently because of the affective relationship developed between Ken and Flicka during the filly's extended illness. Flicka grows to trust and love Ken to the point that she follows him around and neighs excitedly when he appears. Still, Ken is worried that the process of halter-breaking, which he knows entails a certain level of force—ranch horses are usually tied to a fence post until they tire of trying to break themselves free—may force Flicka to again become 'loco' and struggle so hard that she may injure herself. The technique of halter breaking, as carried out throughout the novel on many of the young colts is described as eliciting a confrontation between the animal and the human, a confrontation that ends with the horse's coerced submission:

Invariably, the colt pulled and fought against the rope. He shook his head from side to side, he braced all four feet out straight and stiff. Even grown horses did this, sometimes sitting down, like big dogs. Occasionally, this pulling and fighting went on for a long time, but as a rule, with a young colt, it was soon over. The sudden surrender was almost always expressed in the same manner. The colt would rear straight up, paw the air a moment, then plunge forward to release the pull on his head. That plunge was a movement toward the master—a capitulation; and the colt never forgot it. (191–2)

Conscious of the relationship between Ken and Flicka, Rob McLaughlin devises a method of halter-breaking that uses completely no force whatsoever and relies on Flicka's desire to be with Ken, rather than on eliciting a confrontation between master and animal. Knowing very well that Flicka follows Ken willingly, Rob suggests that Ken simply put a halter on her head:

He summoned all his courage, went to Flicka and held out the halter. Flicka, who loved his hands, and had never felt the touch of them except in gentleness and affection, came closer and Ken slipped the halter over her head, and hooked it under her throat.

‘Now lead her,’ said his father.

Ken obeyed and went down the path twenty yards or so—an easy halt and turn—and back again with Flicka following so close the lead rope was slack.

‘But Dad,’ said Ken, completely dazed, ‘how did she get halter-broke?’

McLaughlin did not answer directly. ‘That’s all folks,’ he said, turning to the small audience. (215)

Because Flicka wants to be with Ken, she simply does what she is used to doing, except that now there is a halter on her head, an accessory the filly does not even notice. The rope never becomes tight and no confrontation ensues. The contrast between these two halter-breaking scenes is stark and reveals that Rob is quite aware that the confrontational character of the process of horse-breaking is not carved in stone but is enmeshed in the complex economic realities of ranch life. The streamlined process of halter-breaking is designed to minimize costs, understood as both material costs and time, and maximize effects. At the same time, excessive emotional attachment between the trainer and the horse is counterproductive: eliciting submission towards a generic human master is the desired goal. Flicka is not being trained to be sold and thus her training does not have to rely on a calculation of investments and gains, though in a sense it appears that Ken’s initial overinvestment of time and affection is now enabling him to experience surprisingly quick gains. The process of halter-breaking fresh colts usually takes the ranch hands a month, and Ken is able to achieve spectacular effects in a matter of minutes.

6. Conclusion: Before the Contact Zone

The scene of Flicka’s halter-breaking seems to be a perfect example of force-free training and of the exciting and productive encounters that take place, as Donna Haraway would put it, in the contact zone. The boy and the horse are acting in unison; they are partners, respectful, and mutually responsive in their ‘dance of relating’ (Haraway 2008, 25). They enjoy one another’s company and seem to want the same things. However, reflecting on what made this situation possible, on what preceded the force-free contact zone encounter, one is reminded of the original violence: of Flicka’s capture, struggle to escape, of her scars and wounds. It cannot be forgotten that this affectionate interspecies relationship was built on

Rob MacLaughlin's advice for Ken to use Flicka's desperation to his advantage, to make her love him.

I have suggested that O'Hara's story can be read as being simultaneously about a particular boy and a particular horse and as a synecdochal representation of domestication as a process. With a tenacious persistence, O'Hara seems to propose a vision of domestication that is rooted in a primal and unavoidable violence. This is why the book foregrounds, early on, the brutal scene of gelding that makes young Ken queasy. Violence is inflicted not joyfully but with an understanding that it is a necessary element of the process of making the animals useful to humans. The streamlined process of breaking catch colts is rooted in the sad rationality of Foucauldian discipline: exert only as much force as needed to obtain the quickest effects. It is also mediated through the notion of encounter value: the affective attachment of the human to the animal grows in result of the animal's responsiveness to training. Even the love story of Ken and Flicka is preceded by the violence that happens before the contact zone encounter can flourish. The original definition of the contact zone, Mary Louise Pratt's definition which Haraway recalls in *When Species Meet*, emphasizes the 'radically asymmetrical relations of power' in contact zone encounters (Haraway 2008, 246). However, productive (even if asymmetrical) relations of power in the contact zone are sometimes enabled by the kind of violence that Foucault would certainly distinguish from disciplinary power.

O'Hara's work is, of course, fiction, and her reading of domestication is a creative interpretation that is rooted in a number of contributing factors. The author's gender, her own life experiences and her position as a woman writer may have contributed to the ambivalence in the representation of taming and breaking—the subplot of Nell and Rob's relationship is unusually detailed for a children's book and could be explored in much greater depth and in relation to biographical and autobiographical materials. The text's setting in the American West, a site of violent conquest and colonization of land, humans, and animals, cannot be separated from the theme of domestication and from the figure of the indomitable mustang. The theme of regeneration through violence has been a constant presence in the mythology of the American frontier (Slotkin 1973). O'Hara's rendering of humans and horses is certainly shaped by and inseparable from these factors, but it is also a certain take on the history of a human-directed evolutionary process—and a very interesting take at that.

While O'Hara's is neither a scientific explanation nor even a creative rendering of a particular scientific theory, her fiction has explanatory potential for what theories of equine domestication, focused on where and when domestication first occurred, gloss over—the

question of how domestication proceeded. Theories of canine domestication are quite focused on the role of canine agency in the process. For example, Lorna and Raymond Coppinger have postulated that dogs self-domesticated themselves by recognizing the refuse generated by human settlements as an easily available food source (Coopinger and Coppinger 2001). Even though other theories suggest that dogs may have become domesticated for different reasons, such as the greater effectiveness of human-canine interspecies packs in procuring food through hunting (Shipman 2017), these theories also stress the active role of dogs in the process. Theories of cat domestication also stress the mutually beneficial character of the association of cats and humans (Francis 2015, Serpell 2000). On the other hand, experts on horse domestication have little to say about horses initiating the process of equine domestication. It is generally assumed, though hardly ever explained in greater detail, that wild horses were forcibly captured by humans and equally forcefully broken. Additionally, a steady influx of wild blood was purposefully maintained in many domestic populations to maintain the animals' hardiness (Francis 2015, 453–4), though again, evolutionary science hardly ever elaborates on the practices associated with maintaining such traits. In other words, O'Hara's creative rendering of the process does not contradict the accounts of evolutionary biologists. On the contrary, her books offer a surprisingly nuanced rendition of the actual encounters that scientific accounts imply but rarely describe in great detail.

O'Hara gives her readers a rendering of domestication as rooted in violence and leaving its mark also on its human agents, who necessarily lose their innocence upon recognizing their role in the process. Domestication is also impermanent, in need of constantly being secured, O'Hara never draws a firm boundary between the wild and the domestic. An uncanny similarity between wild and domestic animals is characteristic of the depictions of animals in this book—not only horses. Nell has a beloved cat by the name of Pauly, a gentle and loving creature that likes to snuggle up on Nell's shoulder. In the last key scene of the book, when Flicka almost dies but for Ken's sacrifice and care—he spends the night holding her head above water as her fever-ridden body cools off in a stream—semi-conscious Ken witnesses an attack by a wildcat on a herd of heifers. In the dreamy rendering of the scene of the attack in Ken's uncomprehending eyes, the feverish boy notes the similarity between the mountain lion in the act of making a kill and Pauly-the-cat: 'The lion pursued [the heifer], low on the ground, like Pauly stalking a bird; it leaped again, executing an extraordinary parabola in the air As the cat curled over the heifer and then fell on its neck, the calf's head was suddenly twisted right around' (248). The wildcat resembles the house cat; tame horses go rogue, while wild-born mustangs are captured and

tamed—domestication fails in its most basic task of establishing a firm boundary between the two realms. Even though Flicka does become gentled, her first colt, Thunderhead, born in captivity and trained by Ken to be a racehorse, is never fully tamed and the second book of the trilogy ends with Ken releasing Thunderhead into the wild mountains of Wyoming. In this sense, rather than reproducing the familiar narrative of colonial progress as the permanent and irreversible domestication of the wild, typical for cowboy narratives like those of J. Frank Dobie or Will James and inherent in the symbolism of the rodeo’s bucking bronco (Nance 2020), O’Hara’s Wyoming trilogy prefigures the contemporary questioning of the wild/domestic binary that takes place in contemporary environmental humanities and animal studies scholarship. It does so by presenting a story that can be read as a metaphor that reveals the complexities of domestication: both the violence inherent in the endeavor and the purely illusory permanence of the process.

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